

Towards Automated Monitoring of Woody Plant Encroachment on Floodplains: A Remote Sensing and Hydrology Framework

Abdullah Toqeer^{1,2}[0009-0007-1764-6333], Andrew Hall²[0000-0001-8213-304X], Ana Horta^{1,2}[0000-0002-1998-8587], and Skye Wassens^{1,2}[0000-0001-8886-8426]

¹ School of Agricultural, Environmental and Veterinary Science, Charles Sturt University, Albury, NSW 2640, Australia.

² Gulbali Institute, Charles Sturt University, Albury, NSW 2640, Australia.
{atoqeer, ahall, ahorta, swassens}@csu.edu.au

Abstract. Woody plant encroachment, the expansion of shrubs and trees into historically herbaceous ecosystems, is accelerating globally across rangelands, savannas, and floodplains, with consequences for biodiversity and hydrology. We present a vision for an automated monitoring framework that fuses multi-source remote sensing data with GeoAI on open platforms (e.g., Open Data Cube/Digital Earth Platforms) to examine floodplain encroachment caused by altered hydrological regimes. The framework combines optical, synthetic aperture radar, structural and hydrological data, applying spatiotemporal analytics to map vegetation change and link it to hydrological drivers. A key feature is the linkage between encroachment dynamics and hydrology: woody expansion trajectories are statistically related to indicators of flow regime, flooding, soil moisture, and groundwater. Using lagged and change-point analyses, the framework can detect thresholds and explain observed patterns without complex hydrological models. Decision-support outputs include maps attributing vegetation changes to drivers and early warnings or triggers for management, such as recommendations for restoring hydrological regimes. The approach is open, reproducible, and scalable, moving beyond mapping where encroachment occurs to explaining why, and enabling earlier interventions.

Keywords: Woody Plant Encroachment · GeoAI · Remote Sensing · Altered Hydrology · Open Data Cube · Digital Earth Platforms · Multi-sensor Fusion

1 Introduction

Woody plant encroachment (WPE) is an increase in the density and cover of shrubs and trees in ecosystems historically dominated by grasses [1], [2]. Over the past 150 years, WPE has been observed across Africa, the Americas, Australia, and Eurasia [3]. For example, non-forested parts of sub-Saharan Africa have seen a roughly 8% rise in woody cover since the 1980s [3]. Such encroachment represents a fundamental land-cover transformation and can precipitate

social-ecological regime shifts as grasslands transition into shrublands or woodlands [4]. Ecologically, WPE often leads to declines in biodiversity and alterations of ecosystem function [2], [5], [6]. As woody plants displace grasses and forbs, specialist flora and fauna (e.g., pollinators and grassland-dependent birds) lose habitat and experience population declines [6].

Multiple factors drive WPE, including altered fire regimes, grazing, landscape fragmentation, and rising CO₂ levels [1], [7]. However, hydrology is frequently the primary control in floodplain and riparian settings [8]. Flood timing, duration, and magnitude govern woody plant recruitment and mortality in these environments [9]. Reduced flooding frequencies or shorter inundation periods increase dry windows for woody seedlings to establish, whereas prolonged or frequent inundation can kill young shrubs and trees [10]. Similarly, multi-year droughts tip the balance in favor of deep-rooted woody plants over shallow-rooted grasses [11]. Lower groundwater levels and loss of river–floodplain connectivity create dry niches where trees and shrubs readily take hold [12], [13]. Once established, woody plants further dry out the system by increasing water loss through evapotranspiration and canopy interception [13]. Given these hydrological influences, our framework centers on flow regimes, inundation, soil moisture, and groundwater metrics, treating other drivers as covariates to ensure clear attribution of cause.

Monitoring WPE is critical for biodiversity conservation and water resource management [2], [14], but ground-based methods are labor-intensive, spatially limited, and often impractical in remote or dense thicket areas [5], [15]. These constraints motivate remote sensing (RS) approaches that exploit analysis ready data (ARD) and GeoAI to detect and quantify woody expansion with minimal fieldwork [16], [17]. Accordingly, we propose a framework that combines multi-source RS data (Optical, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), aerial/Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) imagery) with hydrological indicators (flood and drought records, inundation, soil moisture, groundwater). The aim is to move beyond mapping where encroachment occurs toward understanding why it occurs, thereby yielding information to trigger management interventions. Implemented on open infrastructures such as the Open Data Cube (ODC) framework and Digital Earth platforms (e.g., Australia, Africa, Pacific), the pipeline standardizes preprocessing, enables reproducible spatiotemporal analyses, and scales from local to regional levels. It produces maps of encroachment change and stability, along with layers attributing those changes to hydrological drivers. In the following, we present this hydrology-aware framework as a pathway toward operational WPE monitoring that supports early detection, defensible attribution, and proactive management.

2 Framework Overview

Our hydrology-aware monitoring framework (Fig. 1) consists of three core pillars that together convert multi-source RS data and hydrological context into decision-ready insights:

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework for hydrology-aware monitoring of woody plant encroachment. Multi-source remote sensing (optical, SAR, LiDAR) is integrated with hydrological indicators (flood, drought, inundation, soil moisture, groundwater) on open platforms (e.g., Open Data Cube, Digital Earth). The three pillars transform raw inputs into decision-ready maps, attribution layers, and risk alerts for management. An online-learning feedback loop (periodic retraining) maintains model accuracy over time.

- I. **Multi-sensor benchmarking:** Standardize and fuse inputs from different sensors (optical, LiDAR, SAR) to map woody vs. herbaceous cover. This pillar prepares ARD and applies GeoAI classification models to achieve robust detection of WPE across sensors and resolutions.
- II. **Hydrology linkage:** Relate encroachment patterns to hydrological variables (flows, inundation frequency, soil moisture, groundwater) using statistical attribution techniques. By analyzing how vegetation change correlates with hydrological fluctuations (with appropriate time lags and controls), this pillar identifies key drivers and thresholds. For example, determining if reduced flooding in certain years led to woody plant recruitment events.
- III. **Long-term monitoring and forecasting:** Produce time-series maps of encroachment (showing where woody cover is expanding, stable, or retreating) and short-term forecasts under different hydro-climatic scenarios. Built-in model governance and online learning components (drift checks and peri-

odic retraining) ensure the system gradually adapts to new data and remains accurate over time. Outputs are translated into risk classes or alerts (e.g., emerging encroachment hotspots or predicted responses to drought) to inform management decisions.

Within this framework, mapping refers to classifying woody versus herbaceous cover at a specific point in time, whereas monitoring refers to using these classifications over successive years to track encroachment rates, identify hotspots, and forecast trajectories. By deploying these pillars on open cloud platforms, the framework is scalable and reproducible. All analytical steps are transparent and shareable, facilitating adaptation and reuse across regions.

3 GeoAI and Spatiotemporal Reasoning for Woody Plant Encroachment Monitoring

Remote sensing has long been used to map land cover and vegetation change, but capturing WPE at fine scales presents challenges. While medium-resolution imagery such as Landsat (30 m) provides invaluable long-term temporal records, it often cannot detect scattered shrubs or young trees until they form larger patches [18]. Newer high-resolution sources such as sub-meter aerial photos, drones, and microsatellite imagery now make it possible to discern individual woody plants within a grassland matrix, revealing encroachment that might go unnoticed at coarser scales [6], [18].

Building on these new data sources, advances in machine learning (ML) have transformed how such imagery is analyzed. Our framework is designed to leverage a range of GeoAI models for method and sensor benchmarking, such as baseline classifiers like random forest, support vector machine, and XGBoost [19], while deep-learning architectures like U-Net and ConvLSTM are envisioned for spatial segmentation and temporal forecasting of encroachment. In this paper, we use the term GeoAI to refer to the application of ML and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques to geospatial data, with an emphasis on leveraging spatial and temporal context (e.g., high-resolution image texture or LiDAR-derived canopy height) to distinguish woody vegetation from grasses with greater accuracy [6]. Our framework applies these techniques for continuous monitoring, analyzing multi-temporal imagery (e.g., annual orthomosaics or seasonal composites) to flag new shrubs, estimate encroachment rates, identify hotspots, and forecast spread under different scenarios. This spatiotemporal approach captures WPE’s nonlinear dynamics. Critically, early detection allows managers to intervene with measures like water releases or controlled burns at a stage when these actions can still effectively curb encroachment.

A key component of our pipeline is a classification model integrating spectral, textural, and structural features to separate woody from herbaceous cover. This model will be trained and validated using high-resolution reference data, including field-based surveys and UAV imagery, to ensure robust accuracy. Incorporating structural information (e.g., canopy height) further improves discrimination, with recent studies achieving >97% accuracy using fused imagery

and LiDAR [6]. To maintain performance over time and across regions, we include periodic model retraining (to incorporate new data) and drift detection to address sensor or phenology changes, consistent with the framework’s built-in online-learning design. We also provide basic explainability (highlighting important features) to keep results interpretable for decision-makers. Together, these GeoAI elements learn the subtle signatures of encroachment and adapt as new data arrive, forming the backbone of the automated monitoring system.

4 Remote Sensing Data and Open Infrastructures

The framework exploits multi-sensor RS data to maximize detection performance. Optical, SAR, and LiDAR each provide unique cues (spectral signatures, moisture/structure sensitivity, and 3D canopy height respectively), and together they overcome individual limitations [6], [18], [20]. SAR data complement optical imagery by revealing structural and moisture variations under cloud cover, which is particularly important in floodplain environments where optical observations are often obscured [20]. In practice, the framework draws on multi-generation optical sensors, including Landsat (30 m, since 1986) for long-term trends and Sentinel-2 (10 m) for recent high-resolution detail, together with Sentinel-1 (SAR VV/VH, 10 m), LiDAR (≈ 1 m), and UAV imagery (≤ 0.2 m) to balance spatial coverage, temporal depth, and detail. We draw on open data sources (e.g., National Agriculture Imagery Program aerial imagery, National Ecological Observatory Network LiDAR surveys, Digital Earth Australia ARD data), which have enabled woody cover mapping with $>90\%$ accuracy (reaching 98% when fused) in prior studies [6]. Our workflow runs on open infrastructures such as the ODC and Digital Earth platforms, ensuring scalable and reproducible analysis. All processing code and model parameters are openly documented, aligning with the push for transparent and shareable spatial data science workflows.

5 Integrating Hydrology into the Monitoring Framework

Incorporating hydrology turns our land-cover monitoring system into an ecohydrological observatory that helps explain why encroachment occurs [21]. We integrate RS based hydrological indicators to provide context for vegetation changes. For example, vegetation indices reflect moisture and vegetation water use [22], SAR data shows when and where flooding or soil wetness occurs [23], and thermal infrared data indicate surface drying trends [24]. From these, we derive metrics such as inundation frequency, drought intensity, paired with woody cover change for analysis.

We attribute encroachment to hydrological drivers using statistical analyses. Methods such as lagged regression, distributed-lag non-linear models (DLNM), and change-point tests will quantify the timing and strength of hydrological controls, identify delayed vegetation responses, and detect whether management or climate shifts coincide with woody cover change. Spatial controls and climate

baselines will then be used to estimate attributable expansion, with uncertainty bounds for confidence.

Where available, field data (rainfall, river flow, groundwater, soil moisture) are used to validate and enrich the analysis. Local records may show woody cover increases coinciding with declining runoff or water tables, consistent with studies linking encroachment to reduced streamflow and altered infiltration [25]. Combining in-situ and RS data strengthens causal inference and highlights high-risk areas [14], [21].

Linking vegetation change with hydrological drivers also enables management applications. The framework can highlight areas where encroachment is likely driven by altered hydrology, and identify thresholds or lag times (e.g., woody recruitment surging if a floodplain remains dry >2 years). Such insights translate into actionable triggers, where sites can be flagged for intervention (e.g., environmental water release) before woody takeover occurs.

6 Novelty, Generalizability, and Applications

The primary novelty of this framework is not in its individual components but in its holistic integration. While other studies have used ML for mapping or noted hydrological links, our approach is novel in its design as an end-to-end operational system that formally combines multi-sensor fusion (Pillar 1) with statistical attribution of drivers (Pillar 2) and long-term forecasting (Pillar 3) on a scalable, open platform. Recent studies show that open-access imagery and ML can map woody cover with high accuracy [6], especially when time dynamics are included to provide early warning of regime shifts. Likewise, cloud-based platforms now enable near-real-time, large-scale environmental monitoring [6], [16], and there is growing emphasis on linking encroachment with water cycle changes [21]. Our framework synthesizes these developments and is adaptable to different ecosystems and management needs.

Key features include:

- I. **Multi-source fusion:** Combining optical, radar, and LiDAR data yields more reliable woody-plant detection than any single sensor (each compensates for others' limitations).
- II. **Automated GeoAI:** Trained ML models automatically map encroachment (e.g., producing annual woody cover updates) using open-source tools for transparency and easy transfer to new areas.
- III. **Spatiotemporal insight:** Encroachment is tracked through time, identifying where it is accelerating and linking changes to events (droughts, floods, management), thereby providing early warnings for proactive interventions.
- IV. **Hydrology linkage:** Changes in woody cover are tied to hydrological factors, giving managers actionable information on when and why encroachment surges (e.g., after how long without flooding shrubs begin to dominate).
- V. **Open and generalizable:** Built on public data and open software, the framework is portable and reproducible. It encourages community collaboration, with improvements shared and benchmarked across regions.

Compared with existing land-cover change systems such as LandTrendr or the Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) algorithm, the framework uniquely integrates hydrological indicators to attribute vegetation dynamics to underlying drivers.

7 Conclusion

We have presented a vision for a hydrology-aware GeoAI framework to automate the monitoring of woody plant encroachment, combining multi-sensor remote sensing with statistical linkage to hydrological drivers. By embedding hydrological context into a GeoAI-driven pipeline, our approach moves beyond mapping where encroachment occurs to explaining why it is happening, thereby supporting earlier and more targeted management actions. This framework represents a shift toward proactive, knowledge-driven monitoring that can inform interventions (like restoration of hydrological regimes or managed grazing) before encroachment becomes irreversible.

We invite the community to explore, prototype, and refine this approach. By sharing code, data, and lessons learned openly, researchers and practitioners can collectively advance hydrology-aware monitoring from a conceptual vision to an operational reality. Through such collaboration, environment and water authorities can transition from isolated case studies to scalable, reproducible systems that help anticipate and mitigate woody plant encroachment and its impacts on ecosystems and water resources. Future work will operationalize each component of this framework for large-scale, hydrology-aware monitoring of floodplain vegetation dynamics using open Digital Earth platforms such as Digital Earth Australia.

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